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Gerasimova Svetlana Vasilyevna,
Doctor of Economics, Professor,
Professor of the Department of Business Informatics and Mathematical Modeling,
Institute of Physics and Technology,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

KEY FACTORS OF STOCK MARKET DEVELOPMENT IN CONDITIONS OF ECONOMIC TURBULENCE

The article is devoted to the development of the financial market, which is inextricably linked to the functioning of the entire organizational system and its infrastructure, which includes the financial market, stock exchanges through which trades take place, they are the instrument of the stock and money markets, creating and providing conditions for the interaction of many entities, providing a huge range of related services. The article highlights promising areas for improving anti-crisis tools, including developing an internal investor, diversifying support mechanisms, and increasing the predictability of regulatory policy. The study uses an integrated approach combining monetary, fiscal and institutional measures to ensure the stability of the stock market in the face of global instability. In the process of stock market research, it is considered as the key factors influencing its development in conditions of economic turbulence. Special attention is paid to the relationship between the stock market and the socio-economic development of the country, as well as the consequences of the crisis for financial stability. The study is based on empirical data and statistical analysis, and reveals the degree of dependence of the Russian stock market on external factors. The application of an integrated approach has included a combination of methods in determining the expansion of concessional lending programs and stimulating long-term investments in infrastructure projects that can not only support the stock market, but also contribute to overall economic growth. Based on the above, special attention should be paid to measures to develop the domestic investor, since the high dependence of the stock market on external capital makes it vulnerable in times of crisis.

Keywords: stock market, stock market analysis, financial market, stock market, securities market, integrated approach, currency control.

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08.03.2022 46 « 2 .20 »

[5, 9].

[9].

[1,2,3].

(. 1).

I.

2021-2024

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	2021	2022	2023	2024
	21,7	36,3	60,77	80,13
%	6,6 %	4,6 %	24 %	14 %
	5849,6,	8349,5,	10466,0	14509,09
	22015,4	23843,2	28662,6	46251.3

*

[12].

80,13 2023 38,6 %, 61,4 %, 28,8 %
 3330 65-75 %.
 2024 ,([5, 10]. IT-),

[4, 6].

» [6, 7],
()» [8].

» [5].

[10, 11].

[10].

(.2).

2.

«

4

2023-2024

	2024	2023	2024 2023 , %
	10077	6965	+45 %
	4174	3358	+24 %
	16202	11962	+35 %
	8946	6704	+ 33 %
	5619	7464	-25 %

* [12].

21 %

63

2024

45 %.

25 %».

57 %.

2024

13 IPO (InitialPublicOffering) (
) SPO (SecondaryPublicOffering) (

26

759

8,4

78

27,1 %.

13,5 %.

43,1 %

32,95

30,3 %.

28,3

261,9 %

468

14 %

1,49

2024

[12].

170

(.3).

3.

2020-2024 , . *

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
	82275	91943	80179	95413	108479
	11569	18301	10319	12797	7178
-	70707	78642	69860	93943	101301

* [12].

2023 ,

2022 ,

2023 ,

(.4).

4.

2020-2023

*

	2020	2021	2022	2023
	9889,7	20175,9	29158,4	38981,3
75 %	3	3	3	3
	—	—	16093,1	18795,4
	18870,4	14593,7	22246,1	24579,3

* [12].

25 %

28,4 , 9 2024 521,0 , 53,4 ,
 16,4 ,
 12,3 , 60,7 , 35,1 , 60,0
 20,9 , 287,2 .

[7, 13].

2025 (.5).

[14].

5.
25.08.2025 *

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	7,77 .	299,06
	4,78 .	452,40
	4,51 .	299,15
	3,39 .	131,96
	3,15 .	133,91
	2,58 .	1916,0
	2,58 .	548,45
	1,79 .	115,02
	1,63 .	4188,5
	1,59 .	693,0

* [12, 20].

[21].

[15, 16].

[17, 20].

(.6).
12

2025

4,5

(2,5)
1

10-

22].

17-20%),

(

[19,
2025

10-12% [25].

[18].

(, — , «)

2024

, « »),

2025

2024

« » « »,

50 %

[23, 24].

172

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